

A Study of the Interaction of Selenium Tetrachloride with Substances Containing the Reactive Methylene Group.

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Interactions of 1·3-diketones with selenium tetrachloride seem to have been studied by various workers.* The subject matter of the present paper consists of a study of the interaction of selenium tetrachloride with the substituted amides of malonic acid. It was undertaken with a view to study the reactivity of the hydrogen atoms of the methylene (-CH₂-) group in amides and substituted amides of malonic acid.

In view of the decomposition of selenium tetrachloride studied by Taylor, Prideaux and Pool (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 2129), it is not improbable that in the present interaction it may decompose as—

As such, it was expected that in the present interaction, the reactivity of selenium tetrachloride will be similar to that of sulphur monochloride (Naik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 379). Selenium tetrachloride would, therefore, react with the substituted amides of malonic acid to form either chloro-compounds or selenides of the type, >C=Se.

It is not improbable that in the initial stage of the reaction a diselenide, :C:Se:Se may have been formed, which then passes over into a monoselenide of the type >C:Se. This is not unusual in view of the mechanism of the reaction between ethylene and sulphur monochloride.

That the disulphide (I) passes into the monosulphide (II) was finally settled by the late Lieut. Col. Harrison during the great war. The second sulphur atom in this case behaves as if it were in solution (Naik, *loc. cit.*). The same may be held to be true in the case of the selenides.

* Michaelis and Knuckell, *Ber.*, 1897, **30**, 2828; Morgan and Draw, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, **117**, 1456; *ibid.*, 1922, **121**, 2441; Morgan and Porte, *ibid.*, 1924, **126**, 1372.

In the present case it was found that selenium compounds of the type (b) $>C:Se$, were only formed. It was also interesting to find out the exact conditions under which selenides could be obtained, as also those governing the formation of the chloro-compounds.

With the above purpose in view selenium tetrachloride was made to react with the following substituted amides:—

(1) Malon-diphenylamide, (2) Malon-di-*p*-tolylamide, (3) Malonid-*m*-tolylamide, (4) Malon-di- β -naphthylamide, (5) Methylmalon-di-phenylamide, (6) Methylmalon-di-*p*-tolylamide, (7) Methylmalon-di-*m*-tolylamide, (8) Methylmalon di- β -naphthylamide, (9) Malon-dibenzylamide, (10) Malon-dipropylamide, (11) Malon-diheptylamide, (12) Malon-di(1:3:4)xylidide, (13) Malon-di(1:4:5)xylidide, (14) Malon-di- α -naphthylamide, (15) Malonamide, (16) Malonmonophenylamide, (17) Malonmono-*p*-tolylamide, (18) Malon-*p*-tolylamate, (19) Malonic ester.

The main results of the present investigation can be summarised as under:—

Type I—Amides which interact to form selenides. Compounds from (1) to (8) interact to form selenides of the type, $(-CO\cdot C\cdot CO)_2$.
 Se

Type II—Amides which interact to form chloro-compounds. Compounds from (9) to (13) react to give substances of the type, $\cdot CO\cdot CCl_2\cdot CO\cdot$

Type III—Amides which do not interact with selenium tetrachloride. Substances (14) to (17) do not react.

Compounds (18) and (19) form resinous products with selenium tetrachloride.

Type I.—The first compound of this series was prepared by the action of selenium tetrachloride on malon-diphenylamide in dry ether, at ordinary temperature (27-30°). The course of the reaction can be represented as—

That the reaction actually follows the course shown above is based on the following considerations:—

(1) Of the malon-diphenylamide used, only a small quantity was utilised to form the selenide (I), as was evident from the yield.

(2) The chloro-compound (II) was obtained in a large yield, though it was very difficult to get it in a pure condition, owing to the presence of free selenium in colloidal condition.

(3) The observations of Taylor, Prideux and Pool regarding the decomposition of selenium tetrachloride (*loc. cit.*), also lend support to the view that the reaction follows the course represented by the equation given above.

That the selenide (I) has the constitution shown above is evident from the following observations:—

(i) The two hydrogen atoms eliminated in the formation of the selenide (I) are not those which were originally attached to two nitrogen atoms, because on hydrolysis with aqueous potassium hydroxide, the corresponding derivative of malon-di- β -naphthylamide broke down giving β -naphthylamine.

(ii) The above fact also supports the view that the hydrogens eliminated are not those from the nuclei, for if that were so, β -naphthylamine could not be formed during the hydrolysis.

(iii) That the hydrogens are only removed from the methylene group in the present interaction is further borne out by the reaction of methylmalon-diphenylamide with selenium tetrachloride, where a selenide of the constitution, $(\text{Ph}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{CO})_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)\cdot\text{Se}\cdot\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHPh})_2$ is formed. Here the selenium tetrachloride requires two mono-substituted methylene groups to supply the two necessary hydrogens, in spite of the fact that each molecule of methylmalon-diphenylamide has two hydrogens available either from those attached to the nitrogens or from the two nuclei.

It is evident, therefore, that the formula assigned to the selenide of malon-diphenylamide is correct. On considerations which led Morgan and his co-workers to represent selenium as tetravalent, the selenide (I) of malon-diphenylamide may be represented as—

As the selenides so obtained, are all insoluble in ordinary solvents, it was found very difficult to determine the molecular weight of any of these compounds. The stability of these selenides when treated with sodium bisulphite, which should reduce them to the corresponding substituted malonamides, goes to strengthen the view that selenium here is rather tetravalent than divalent.

Returning now to the dichloro-compound (II), one is led to believe that the two chlorine atoms are in the nuclei, for, on trying to

reduce the dichloro-compound with hydrogen iodide by Kurt Meyer's method. the dichloro-compound was obtained unchanged. This compound is, therefore, different from the dichloromalon-diphenylamide $\text{CCl}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NHPh})_2$ obtained by Naik and Shah (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 4, 12) by the interaction of sulphuryl chloride and malon-diphenylamide. That the two chlorine atoms of compound (II) are in the nuclei is further borne out by the fact that on hydrolysis with aqueous potash it yielded *m*-chloroaniline.†

It seems curious that in the compound (II) the halogens should prefer the nuclear hydrogens to those of the reactive methylene group. This behaviour is easily explained on the considerations of the results obtained by Silberrad and Park (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2449), who pointed out that in the presence of chlorides of selenium as catalysts, chlorination of benzene derivatives takes place preferably in the nucleus rather than in the side-chain.

From the above it follows that the dichloro-compound (II) should be represented as $\text{CH}_2(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NH}\cdot\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$.

The constitution of the two main products of the present interaction having been thus established, reactions of other substituted amides with selenium tetrachloride were tried.

Malon-di-*p*- and -*m*-tolylamides and malon-di- β -naphthylamide reacted with selenium tetrachloride giving rise to the selenides of the type $(\text{RNH}\cdot\text{CO})_2\text{C}:\text{Se}:\text{Se}:\text{C}(\text{CO}\cdot\text{NER})_2$.

In order to study whether the same type of reactivity persisted throughout the corresponding derivatives of methylmalonic acid, the following four amides, namely (5) (6), (7), and (8) (*vide supra*) were subjected to the action of selenium tetrachloride, when it was found that selenides of the general structure, $>\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)\cdot\text{Se}\cdot\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)<$ were formed.

It may be noted here that malonamide, malon-monophenylamide and malonmono-*p*-tolylamide were found not to react with selenium tetrachloride. Thus the reactivity which only began to manifest itself in the case of the dianilides and ditolylamides was increasing rapidly in the case of malon-*o*- and -*p*-tolylamides, and reached its

† That the product of hydrolysis is *m*-chloroaniline is substantiated on the following grounds :—

(i) The acetyl (m.p. 71°) and the benzoyl derivatives (m.p. 120°) of the product were found to be identical with those obtained from *m*-chloroaniline.

(ii) *p*-Dichloromalonanilide melts at 261° (Chattaway and Mason, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 87, 840), whereas our dichloro-compound melts at 175°-76°.

maximum in the case of malonic ester itself, so much so, that in the last two cases resinous products were obtained. Thus, the experimental observations afford a clear evidence that the interaction of selenium tetrachloride with the amides enumerated above depends on the total negativity of the groups attached to the two remaining valencies of the methylene carbon atom. If this carry neutral groups such as $-\text{CONH}_2$ as in malonamide, no interaction occurs. Even when the neutral character of one of the $-\text{CONH}_2$ groups is disturbed by a phenyl or a tolyl group, interaction does not start. But when the neutral character of both the $-\text{CONH}_2$ groups is disturbed by converting them into $-\text{CONHPh}$ group, the reactivity starts. In a series like,

the reactivity which is absent in (i) and (ii) starts in (vi) and goes on increasing, lesser and lesser time being required for the completion of the reaction. Finally in the case of (v) and (vi) the reaction proceeds so vigorously that resinous products are obtained.

The interaction of selenium tetrachloride with the amides enumerated under Type II, resulted in the formation of dichloro-compounds, thus:

In all these cases the halogens replaced the hydrogens original attached to the methylene carbon atom, as was evident from the fact that when such compounds were treated with potassium iodide and concentrated hydrochloric acid, the halogens were easily reduced. Of the five compounds thus prepared two, name dichloromalon-dipropylamide and dichloromalon-dibenzylamide were identical with those prepared by Naik and Shah (*loc. cit.*). The other three are new and their constitutions are established on the same considerations as in the case of the first two dichloro compounds. Such a type of chlorinating action of selenium tetrachloride has already been reported by Morgan and Drew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 119, 1452).

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method of Preparation.—The amide (5 mols.) was made to react with selenium tetrachloride (4 mols.) suspended in anhydrous ether. The reactions were carried out at ordinary temperature carefully excluding moisture. Hydrogen chloride was evolved during the course of the reaction. At the end of the reaction, (usually after 8 or 10 hours) the ether was slowly evaporated off and a greenish-yellow product coated with a thin film of selenium (red variety) was obtained. The dry mass was then repeatedly extracted with dry benzene, till no red film was formed on the product on drying. To ascertain that the compound was free from selenium metal, it was treated with reduced copper gauze in boiling benzene, until the shining surface of the copper gauze no longer blackened. The product was thus completely freed from selenium.

Selenomalon-diphenylamide.—Malon-diphenylamide (1.5 g.) was made to react with selenium tetrachloride (1.0 g.) in 50 c.c. of anhydrous ether. Selenomalon-diphenylamide was isolated and purified as mentioned above. The substance was insoluble in alcohol, chloroform, benzene, ether, petroleum, carbon disulphide, carbon tetrachloride, toluene, xylene, acetic acid and acetone. It was soluble in aniline and pyridine, but on evaporating the solvents, the substance was found to have been decomposed into the original malon-diphenylamide and elemental selenium (yellowish-green amorphous powder.) It darkened at 217° and melted at 222-223° to a clear red liquid. (Found: Se, 22.98. $C_{30}H_{24}N_4O_4Se_2$ requires Se, 23.86 per cent.)

Reduction of Selenomalon-diphenylamide.—On reduction with alkaline hydrosulphide (Brand, Ber., 1906, 42, 3464) selenomalon-diphenylamide was transformed into malon-diphenylamide and hydrogen selenide. The hydrogen selenide thus formed deposited selenium (red variety) on standing, the malon-diphenylamide obtained having been identified.

Bromination of Selenomalon-diphenylamide.—When compound (I) was treated with bromine, selenium bromide was produced together with $CBr_2(CO \cdot NHPh)_2$, which was found to be identical with the compound of Backes, West and Whiteley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 874).

Malon-dichlorodiphenylamide.—In the course of the above reaction malon-diphenylamide was partly converted into malondichloro-phenylamide. This substance was obtained in benzene solution, used in the

extraction of selenomalon-diphenylamide. On evaporating benzene malon-dichlorodiphenylamide was obtained as a crude sticky red powder. On repeated crystallisation it was obtained in the form of colourless cubic crystals from alcohol, m.p. 175-76°. (Found: Cl, 21.70. $C_{15}H_{12}N_2O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 21.96 per cent.)

Hydrolysis of Malon-dichlorodiphenylamide.—The dichloro-compound (2.0 g.) was mixed with an aqueous solution of caustic potash (5 g. NaOH in 10 c.c.). The whole was then refluxed for three hours. A red-brown liquid separated. This was extracted with ether, and after purification was identified as *m*-chloroaniline (b. p. 231°).

Selenomalon-di-p-tolylamide.—Malon-di-*p*-tolylamide (1.5 g.) and selenium tetrachloride (1 g.) in 50 c.c. anhydrous ether were employed and the resulting selenomalon-di-*p*-tolylamide was obtained after purification, as a yellow powder, m. p. 218-219°. The behaviour of this substance towards solvents was similar to that of selenomalon-diphenylamide. (Found: Se, 22.09. $C_{34}H_{32}N_4O_4Se_2$ requires Se, 22.01 per cent.)

Selenomalon-di-m-tolylamide.—This was obtained in the same way as the *para*-derivative and had in similar properties, the time required for the completion of the reaction was less in this case. It melted at 210-211°, darkening previously at 205°. (Found: Se, 21.75. $C_{34}H_{32}N_4O_4Se_2$ requires Se, 22.04 per cent.)

Selenomalon-di-β-naphthylamide.—Selenium tetrachloride (1 g.), suspended in 60 c.c. of anhydrous ether was made to react with malon-di-β-naphthylamide (1.3 g.), the reaction mixture being kept overnight. Selenomalon-di-β-naphthylamide, m.p. 220°, was obtained after the usual procedure. (Found: Se, 18.26. $C_{46}H_{32}N_4O_4Se_2$ requires Se, 18.32 per cent.)

Hydrolysis of Selenomalon-di-β-naphthylamide.—One g. of the selenide was refluxed for two hours with 20 c.c. of alcoholic potash (1 g.) when a buff-coloured solution was obtained. A flocculent white mass separated on pouring the solution into a large excess of water. This was subsequently identified to be β-naphthylamine, m. p. 111°. The filtrate deposited red selenium on standing.

Selenomethylmalon-diphenylamide.—Methylmalon-diphenylamide (2 g.) and selenium tetrachloride (1.5 g.) in 60 c.c. of anhydrous ether were used. The substance resembled the corresponding malon-diphenylamide derivative in its behaviour; m. p. 222-224°. (Found: Se, 12.42. $C_{32}H_{30}N_4O_4Se$ requires Se, 12.87 per cent.)

Selenomethylmalon-di-p-tolylamide.—The amide (2.5 g.) in 25 c. c. of dry ether and selenium tetrachloride (1.0 g.) gave a

product which was purified in the usual way. It blackens at 210° and melts at 224-225°. (Found: Se, 11·76. $C_{36}H_{34}N_4O_4Se$ requires Se, 11·95 per cent.).

Selenomethylmalon-di-m-tolylamide.—This was obtained in the form of a yellow amorphous powder by the interaction of 2·5 g. of the amide with 1 g. of selenium tetrachloride. It melted at 221°. (Found: Se, 11·63. $C_{36}H_{34}N_4O_4Se$ requires Se, 11·95 per cent.).

Selenomethylmalon-di-β-naphthylamide.—The selenide was prepared in the usual way from 8 g. of the amide and 1·0 g. of selenium tetrachloride. It was a yellow powder insoluble in all organic solvents and melted at 229-230°. (Found: Se, 9·33. $C_{48}H_{42}N_4O_4Se$ requires Se, 9·71 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-diheptylamide.—Malon-diheptylamide (1·5 g.) was treated with selenium tetrachloride (1 g.) in 30 c.c. of dry ether. At the end of 10-12 hours, both the amide and the selenium tetrachloride went into solution (pink). On evaporating the solution by means of hot air, a red pasty residue was obtained. On treatment with alcohol the pink film of red selenium was precipitated and a fairly colourless solution of the dichloro-compound was obtained. After repeated crystallisations, the substance was obtained in colourless, stout, prismatic needles, m. p. 90°. It was soluble in alcohol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, ether, acetic acid and acetone. (Found: Cl, 19·05. $C_{17}H_{32}N_2O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 19·34 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-di(1:3:4)xylylide.—This substance was obtained from malon-di(1:3:4)xylylide (1·8 g.) and selenium tetrachloride (1·0 g.) in 50 c.c. of anhydrous ether. The pure sample formed fine colourless needles melting at 136-137°. (Found: Cl, 18·09. $C_{19}H_{20}N_2O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 18·53 per cent.).

Dichloromalon-di(1:4:5)xylylide.—This was obtained in the same way as the previous xylylide. On crystallisation it was obtained as colourless, shining, short needles, m. p. 170°. (Found: Cl, 18·26. $C_{19}H_{20}N_2O_2Cl_2$ requires Cl, 18·73 per cent.).

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